

Predicting the size of silver nanoparticles synthesised in flow reactors: Coupling population balance models with fluid dynamic simulations

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ABSTRACT

Achieving size control during nanomaterial synthesis is critical for their deployment in numerous applications due to their strong size-properties relationships. However, it remains a challenge in the field due to multi-step mechanisms in nanoparticle synthesis. In this paper, we present an experimentally-validated model able to predict the particle size and distribution of silver nanoparticles synthesised in flow reactors by coupling time-resolved fluid dynamic simulations with population balance. The model reveals fundamental correlations between reactor design and the corresponding size of the nanoparticles. It shows that increasing mixing rate, increases the overall rate of nanoparticle formation, where nanoparticle synthesis takes place homogeneously in the whole of the reaction volume. In contrast, when there is a distinguishable interface between reactant streams (i.e. low mixing rate), nucleation and growth take place in a small fraction of the reaction volume in the interface between the inlet streams. The combination of fast mixing and high average nucleation rate can lead to a burst of nuclei formation translated in small size and narrow size distribution. This work presents a new approach for the use of computational-guided design of reactors for the synthesis of nanomaterials to move the field away from current trial-and-error strategies.

1. Introduction

Metal nanoparticles have been widely studied in past decades due to their unique properties (catalytic, optical, electronic, magnetic, etc [1–6]). Such physical and chemical properties are strongly dependent on the size and shape of the metal nanoparticles [7,8], making size distribution and size control critical during their synthesis. For instance, in the case of catalysis, the metal size strongly affects its catalytic activity as it determines the surface energy, strain and defects and thus, their interactions with different molecules [9,10]. Optical properties such as extinction, absorption, and scattering are also size-dependent, with potentially different optimum size for biomedical, energy, and information technologies [4,11]. Magnetic properties such as magnetic moment, the anisotropy constant or the interplay between the core and surface properties of the nanoparticles are also affected by the size and influence their performance in nanomedicine [12,13]. A range of approaches have been developed over the last years to control the size of nanomaterials, including the use of capping ligands (wet chemistry), vapour deposition methodologies and laser ablation (physical methods).

More recently, our group and other researchers have demonstrated that controlling transport phenomena during the synthesis, especially in the early stages (i.e. rate at which homogeneous mixing is achieved) affects the nucleation rate, playing a key role in controlling the final size and distribution of the nanomaterial [14–18]. Various parameters can affect the mixing efficiency. In batch reactors, mixing is normally promoted by active systems (e.g. stirrers and propellers). Their efficiency is primarily affected by the reaction volume, the mixer design and the stirring speed. In contrast, mixing in flow reactors is passive and mostly depends on the mixer and reactor designs. To gain a better understanding and quantify transport phenomena in reactors, computational fluid dynamic (CFD) simulations have been widely used [19–22].

Similarly, a number of mechanistic models have been developed for the synthesis of nanoparticles, considering nucleation and growth. In particular, the Population Balance Equation (PBE) is a mathematical framework used to describe the evolution of a population of particles or entities concerning a specific property or characteristic (size, mass, composition, etc.). It provides a platform to calculate the size and size distribution of metal nanoparticles considering the kinetic rates of both

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Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the reaction system and the coupled computational approach. The geometry of the reactor after the T-mixer is varied from a straight flow reactor (SFR) to a helical flow reactor (HFR) as shown in the figure. The Figure shows planes cuts along the length of the reactor to follow the evolution of a given property, e.g. evolution of the concentration of AgNO_3 .

nucleation and growth stages. It has been previously applied mainly in the field of aerosol science, particle technology and environmental engineering [23–26].

Coupling of PBM (Population Balance Model) and CFD provides a unique opportunity to describe the synthesis of nanoparticles by understanding the formation of polydisperse entities in complex fluid behaviours, with lower computational cost than other approaches, such as a purely Lagrangian framework [11]. Such coupled PBM-CFD methods have been previously reported to describe the formation of particles and droplets in two-phase systems such as bubble columns [27–32], and in crystallisation systems (without considering the chemical reactions) [33–35]. In recent years, substantial efforts have been invested in the development of couple PBM-CFD models for the synthesis of silver nanoparticle [36–39]. A recent review compiles much of this research [40]. However, previous attempts of coupled PBM-CFD methods for AgNPs synthesis do not show kinetic parameters, rigorous consideration

of diffusion coefficients in microchannels [36] or predictive capabilities [36,38,41]. This work provides visual information on the evolution of the particle density, mean size and size distribution as a function of mixing degree in the reactor in helicoidal reactors. Herein, we present an experimentally validated PBM-CFD simulation methodology to accurately predict the impact of flow characteristics and reaction conditions on the evolution of size and distribution, using the synthesis of silver nanoparticles via chemical reduction as a showcase. The predictive capabilities of this methodology will lead to a better design of flow reactors guided by CFD, avoiding trial-and-error approaches.

2. Description of the modelled system

This work considers the formation of silver nanoparticles (Ag NPs) via chemical reduction of silver nitrate (AgNO_3) precursor using sodium borohydride (NaBH_4) as a strong reducing agent according to the

Table 1
Summary of the studied reactor configurations.

Case Number	Reactor	Total flow rate (mL min^{-1})*	Residence time (s)	T (C)	Diameter helix (mm)	Re	De
1	HFR	0.7	23.3	60	14	40	9.6
2	HFR	0.7	23.3	60	28	40	6.8
3	HFR	0.7	23.3	60	100	40	3.6
4	SFR	0.7	23.3	60	∞	40	0
5	HFR	0.15	108.9	60	14	9	2.1
6	HFR	0.5	32.7	60	14	30	6.9
7	HFR	1.4	11.7	60	14	80	18.7
8	HFR	2.1	7.8	60	14	120	28.8
9	HFR	0.7	23.3	75	14	50	9.6
10	HFR	0.7	23.3	90	14	60	9.6

*After the T-mixer, with equal flow rates in each of the inlets.

Total reactor length: 0.6 m total reactor length. Tube inner diameter: 0.76 mm.

In helical configurations, the pitch distance was constant at $1/\pi$ mm.

SFR: Straight Flow Reactor; HFR: Helical Flow Reactor.

general reaction:

Details of the experimental procedure can be found in the [Supplementary information](#).

To accurately model the synthesis of Ag NPs in microreactors, a coupled computational tool has been developed, as depicted in [Fig. 1](#). The reactants (aqueous solutions of AgNO_3 and NaBH_4) are mixed in T-mixer with a cross-flow configuration with an inner diameter of 2.3 mm. The AgNO_3 stream is introduced normal to the mixer tube direction with a concentration of 0.1 mM, while the NaBH_4 is introduced perpendicular to the reactor with a concentration of 0.6 mM. The distance between the mixer and the inlet of the reactor is 10 mm. Time = 0 refers at the inlet of the reactor. Two different reactor configurations have been used, a straight flow reactor (SFR) and a 3D helical flow reactor (HFR), where the reaction tube is curved on a cylindrical support of diameter D (i.e. helical diameter). The inner diameter and length of the tube were set at 0.76 mm and 0.6 m, respectively (to mimic the experimental dimensions [\[37\]](#)). For the helical reactor, three different helical diameters were modelled, 14, 28 and 100 mm, with a fixed pitch distance of $1/\pi$ mm. The different reactor configurations used in the study are summarised in [Table 1](#).

The fully miscible aqueous inlet streams containing the reactants form the primary liquid phase 1, while the solid phase 2 consists of the in-situ formed silver nanoparticles. The simulation of the system requires the simultaneous and coupled solution of 3 different models: i. The [multiphase model](#) (based on the mixture model) to calculate the velocity and pressure fields for both phases, ii. The [species transport model](#) for the primary phase and the iii. [Population balance model](#) using the quadrature method of moments (QMOM) to simulate the formation and growth of nanoparticles. ANSYS Fluent v. 2019 R2 was used for solving the three models.

The mesh was done using ANSYS-ICEM, with around 6 million elements, a global element seed size of $7 \cdot 10^{-6}$ m and 14 nodes from the 0-Grid block diagonal. Two spacing regions were used (size 1: $2 \cdot 10^{-5}$ m, ratio 1.3; size 2: $4 \cdot 10^{-5}$, ratio 2) to generate a refinement close to the tube wall.

i. Population balance model

The synthesis of silver nanoparticles via chemical reduction is simulated using the Finke-Watzky pseudo elementary two-step mechanisms [\[42\]](#). The mechanism operates on the assumption of a pseudo first-order reaction. This simplifies the calculation of local values such as rate of nanoparticle formation, nuclei size and surface growth for each of the differential fluid cells in the reactor. The two-step mechanism considers a first nucleation step followed by growth. Although the nucleation step is normally considered a pseudo-first order reaction, in this case, the concentration of the reducing agent is included in the rate of nucleation reaction to incorporate the mixing effects in the nucleation rate expression. In other words, nucleation can only take place in the presence of reducing agent and the metal precursor.

The rate of growth is expressed as:

where k_{nuc} (particles $\text{m}^{-3}\text{M}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$) and k_{growth} ($\text{mM}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$) are the apparent kinetic constants for nucleation and growth, respectively. These values were estimated using experimental data, as explained in the results section.

The population balance equation given by [Eq \(3\)](#) is expressed using the characteristic length or particle diameter (L [m]) as the internal coordinate [\[43\]](#). It represents the change in particle size distribution in a

differential cell in the Finite Volume Method, considering the incoming and outgoing particles flow and the net generation at position x . The generation term considers changes in the total number of particles due to nucleation and changes in the distribution of sizes due to growth.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} n(L; x, t) + \nabla \cdot [\vec{u} n(L; x, t)] = -\frac{\partial}{\partial L} [G(L)n(L; x, t)] \quad (3)$$

At steady-state conditions, the equation can be simplified as shown in [Eq. \(4\)](#):

$$\nabla \cdot [\vec{u} n(L; x)] = -\frac{\partial}{\partial L} [G(L)n(L; x)] \quad (4)$$

where the term $n(L; x, t)$ is the normalised density function (NDF) and represents the statistical distribution of sizes (L [m]) and its evolution with position (x [m]) and time (t [s]), \vec{u} is the particle velocity vector [m/s]. Note that this equation does not take into consideration aggregation, agglomeration or breakage of particles. Disregarding the aggregation and breakage term of the PBE was done based on previous computational works in which Ag-NPs NDF are modelled [\[36,38\]](#), and the support of our previous experimental evidence [\[37\]](#). In the same conditions of the present study, increasing the length of the helical reactor (once full reduction of the silver ions is achieved), similar average diameter and size distribution were observed for different reactor lengths, suggesting that aggregation is negligible under the studied flow conditions. However, these simplifications must be carefully examined for other systems or under different conditions.

To solve the PBE for the unknown NDF, the Quadrature Method of Moments (QMOM) approximation method is used. This method could potentially be used to incorporate size-dependent growth kinetics, but this has not been considered in this study. In this model definition, growth depends on the solid silver formed [Ag^*], which is calculated as part of the mass transfer and is directly proportional throughout the domain to the value of moment 3.

QMOM method defines the distribution of particle sizes at each domain by the function moments (properties of the statistical distribution of sizes), solving the transport, accumulation, and generation of these moments. Four moments are used in this study: m_0 represents the total number of particles, m_1 the total particles length (m), m_2 the total area (m^2), and m_3 the total volume of solid particles (m^3), all obtained per unit volume of the solution. A higher number of moments could increase accuracy, but at the expense of increasing computational requirements. Furthermore, this also depends on the complexity of the experimental particle distributions to model. In this study, given that the experimental data indicates size distributions with no complex asymmetric Gaussian type, we have deemed that 4 moments are sufficient to capture such distribution profiles.

Moments are calculated through a series of weights and abscissas, where integrals are approximated and solved numerically using a Gaussian Quadrature [\[44,45\]](#). As a result, the j -th order moments can be computed by:

$$m_j(x, t) = \int_{d_{\text{nuc}}}^{d_{\text{max}}} n(L; x, t) L^j dL \approx \sum_{i=1}^N w_i L_i^j, j = 0, 1, \dots, 2N - 1 \quad (5)$$

where w_i are the weights, L_i are the abscissas and N is the total number of weights or abscissas. j is the index for the number of the moment being solved (0 to 3 herein). The integral is calculated by N 's weights and abscissas of order $2N-1$.

[Eq. \(5\)](#) can be written in the following expanded form (for $N = 2$):

$$\begin{aligned} m_0 &= w_1 + w_2 \\ m_1 &= L_1 w_1 + L_2 w_2 \\ m_2 &= L_1^2 w_1 + L_2^2 w_2 \\ m_3 &= L_1^3 w_1 + L_2^3 w_2 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

From an initial set of moments (in this simulation with zero value), initial abscissas and weights can be calculated but the direct solution requires a non-linear solver. McGraw [44] proposed to use the product-difference (PD) algorithm [46] to find the abscissas and weights (for the usually called moment inversion algorithm in the field of PBM), by writing the recursive relationship for the polynomials in terms of the moments m_j . This relationship is written in matrix form, the roots of the polynomials correspond to the eigenvalues of the Jacobi matrix. The procedure and exact equations are described in McGraw 1997 [44], Appendix A, Inversion of moments sequences.

Once the moments are defined in Eq. (6), Eq. (4) is transformed in ANSYS Fluent QMOM when only nucleation and growth are included, to:

$$\nabla [\vec{u}^j m_j] = 0^j N_R + j G_R m_{j-1} = 0^j N_R + j G_R (L_1^{j-1} w_1 + L_2^{j-1} w_2) \quad (7)$$

One inconvenience we encountered while conducting this work is that the 0^j term will be 1 if $j = 0$, and 0 elsewhere, meaning that nucleation rate only affects moment 0 (number of particles).

In the other hand, the growth term is null for moment 0. This combination leads to the generation of zero diameter particles that grow afterwards. There is no increase in total diameter, total area, or total volume due to nucleation (m_1, m_2, m_3 remain unchanged) and thus, there is no mass transfer.

Eq. (8) is an evolution of previous approaches (and the default equation in ANSYS Fluent) to avoid the generation of nuclei with null diameters.

$$\nabla \cdot [\vec{u}^j m_j] = d_{nuc}^j N_R + j G_R (L_1^{j-1} w_1 + L_2^{j-1} w_2) \quad (8)$$

where the advective transport of the moment is expressed as a function of the nuclei size (d_{nuc} , in this case, 10^{-9} m), the nucleation rate (N_R) and the growth rate (G_R) (both introduced as user functions as per Eqs. (1) and (2)). Note that to implement the change, an additional term was added for each of the moments.

Initial abscissas and weights calculated with Eq. (6) are used in Eq. (7) to obtain new values of moments. These moments are then used in Eq. (6) to recalculate abscissas and weights, and this calculation cycle repeats at each iteration.

Finally, given a set of moments, ANSYS Fluent estimates the most likely PSD based on the "statistically most probable" distribution for turbulent flames [47]. ANSYS Fluent models the Number Density Function as an exponential function [48]:

$$n(L) = \exp\left(\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} A_i L^i\right) = \exp(A_0 + A_1 L + A_2 L^2 + A_3 L^3) \quad (9)$$

where the A_i are the coefficients of a polynomial function. The equation of each moment is now written as [47,48]:

$$m_j = \int_{d_{nuc}}^{d_{max}} L^j \exp\left(\sum_{i=0}^{2N-1} A_i L^i\right) dL, j = 0, 1, \dots, 2N - 1 \quad (10)$$

The calculation of the A_i coefficients requires a non-linear solver, in this case, the globally convergent Newton-Raphson method is used in ANSYS Fluent. To integrate Eq. (10) for each moment, Fluent uses a constant 100 diameter discretization in the PSD reconstruction. The upper limit of the particle diameter needs to be large enough to represent the whole range of sizes but low enough to provide accuracy in the method. In this case, an upper diameter of 10^{-7} m is used based on the experimental observations.

ii. Species transport model for the primary liquid phase

The species transport model is used to calculate the concentration evolution of the two liquid streams across the reactor. As both streams are diluted aqueous solutions, the physical properties of water (density,

Table 2

Physical properties at different temperatures.

T	$D_{AgNO_3,m}$	$D_{NaBH_4,m}$	μ (mixture)	Re
°C	$m^2 s^{-1}$	$m^2 s^{-1}$	$kg m^{-1} s^{-1}$	
60	$3.55 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$5.97 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$0.46 \cdot 10^{-3}$	40
75	$4.60 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$7.25 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$0.38 \cdot 10^{-3}$	50
90	$5.81 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$8.67 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$0.31 \cdot 10^{-3}$	60

and viscosity, μ) are used (Table 2). As the mixing of reactants at low Reynolds numbers (range studied in this work is between 9 and 120) is likely to be dominated by diffusion, special attention has been paid for the estimation of accurate diffusion coefficients (D) extrapolating experimental data from the literature [49,50].

For the primary phase the mass conservation equation for each individual chemical specie c (subscript) in the computational domain, can be expressed as:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho Y_c) + \nabla \cdot (\rho \vec{v} Y_c) = \nabla \cdot J_c + R_c \quad (11)$$

where Y_c is the mass fraction of a species c in the mixture (dimensionless), J_c is its diffusive flux ($kg m^{-2} s^{-1}$) and R_c its rate of production/consumption ($kg m^{-3} s^{-1}$), determined by the coupling with the Population Balance Model. The velocity vector, \vec{v} (m/s), couples the mass balances to the hydrodynamics calculations. The diffusive flux can be estimated using Fick's first law of diffusion (Eq. (12)), being $D_{c,m}$ the diffusion coefficient of the chemical specie c in the mixture:

$$J_s = -\rho D_{c,m} \nabla Y_c \quad (12)$$

iii. Multiphase model

The multiphase modelling capability of ANSYS Fluent is used. The *mixture model* is chosen as it can capture the evolving distribution of particle sizes (dispersed phase) within the primary flow field without a high computational cost [51], as previously demonstrated for similar systems [36]. This model solves only one momentum equation for the n-phases being transported and describes the flow of each phase (for the liquid and solid phases) defining a relative velocity. The mean diameter of the nanoparticle distribution is used to compute the global resistance to flow in a cell, instead of being individual solid particles affecting the flow. For the slip velocity, the Manninen et al. formulation [52] was used to describe the algebraic relationship for the relative velocity. The collisional and frictional solid stress is neglected. Nanoparticles are considered to have spherical shapes.

The calculation of the velocity field for the secondary solid phase is achieved by coupling the PBM and the multiphase fluid dynamic calculation using the Sauter mean diameter d_{32} , defined as the ratio of moment 3 (m_3 , particles volume, m^3) and moment 2 (m_2 , particles surface, m^2):

$$d_{32} = \frac{m_3}{m_2} \quad (13)$$

To generate the secondary solid phase, the mass transfer coupling rates between the primary (liquid) and secondary (solid) phases (Mt , $kmol_{Ag,s} m^{-3} s^{-1}$) are defined by again coupling the PBM and the multiphase fluid dynamic model as shown in Eqs. (14) and (15):

$$Mt_{Ag,s}(nucleation) = \frac{\rho_{Ag,s}}{Mw_{Ag,s}} \frac{\pi}{6} d_{nuc}^3 N_R \quad (14)$$

$$Mt_{Ag,s}(growth) = \frac{\rho_{Ag,s}}{Mw_{Ag,s}} \frac{\pi}{6} 3 G_R m_2 \quad (15)$$

where $\rho_{Ag,s}$ and $Mw_{Ag,s}$ are the density and molecular weight of the secondary phase (i.e. silver) and $\pi/6$ is the sphericity constant.

Table 3

Apparent nucleation and growth kinetic constants for the synthesis of silver nanoparticles via chemical reduction.

T (C)	k_{nuc} (particles $m^{-3} \cdot M^{-2} \cdot s^{-1}$)	k_{Growth} (m $\cdot M^{-2} \cdot s^{-1}$)
60	$6 \cdot 10^{26*}$	$4 \cdot 10^{-1*}$
75	$3.89 \cdot 10^{27**}$	1.19^{**}
90	$2.16 \cdot 10^{28**}$	3.23^{**}

* Estimated using experimental data.

** Calculated considering an Arrhenius relationship.

For the calculation of the slip velocity, an algebraic relationship with the relative velocity previously formulated [53] was used, where the collisional and frictional solid stress are neglected.

Equations for velocity vectors, continuity, concentration of reactants, moments 1–4 and volume fraction of phases 1 and 2 are solved simultaneously. The segregated steady-state solver was used to solve the governing equations and find a steady-state solution by breaking down the solution process into steps for different variables (such as pressure and velocity) and iteratively solving them until the solution stabilizes. QUICK discretisation scheme was employed for cell interpolation except for pressure for which the standard method was selected. The Semi-Implicit Method for Pressure-Linked Equations (SIMPLE algorithm) was chosen for the solve the interdependent pressure–velocity coupling. Convergence of the numerical solution was ensured by monitoring the scaled residuals to a criterion of at least 10^{-6} . Additionally, the variables of interest have been monitored at different surfaces of the computational domain as indicators of convergence (at least 100 iterations without changes).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Determination of the apparent kinetic constants using experimental data

The apparent kinetic nucleation and growth constants of the Finke-Watzky two-step mechanism for the synthesis of silver nanoparticles were estimated using experimental data from [37]. For that, a helical reactor with the same dimensions that those of the computational model was used (helix diameter, D: 14 mm, pitch distance: $1/\pi$, length: 0.6 m, tube inner diameter: 0.76 mm). Silver nanoparticles were synthesised using a total flowrate of 0.7 mL min^{-1} at 60C. The values of the apparent kinetic constants k_{nuc} and k_{growth} were estimated using an iterative process, where their values are iteratively varied to minimise the difference between the experimental particle size distribution at the outlet of the reactor (Case 1 in Table 1) and the simulated one (Table 3).

In this way, the apparent nucleation kinetic constant, k_{nuc} , is estimated as $6 \cdot 10^{26}$ particles $m^{-3} M^{-2} s^{-1}$ (or 0.01 min^{-1} considering the concentration of reactants and silver molecular weight). This estimated value is within range of the recently published review data ($1.8 \cdot 10^{-8}$ to 0.031 min^{-1}), strongly dependent on the metal precursor and reducing agent used as expected [40]. Similarly, the apparent growth kinetic

constant, k_{growth} , is estimated as $4 \cdot 10^{-1} \text{ m M}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. It is difficult to compare this value with those reported in the literature as our population balance model defines the growth rate in m/s, while literature data express Eq. (2) in terms of molar production of AgNPs, providing values of k_{growth} with units of $M^{-1} s^{-1}$, making their comparison unfeasible [40,54]. The reader should exercise caution when extrapolating the kinetic parameters.

Fig. 2 demonstrates that the estimated apparent nucleation and growth kinetic constants result in a prediction of particle size distribution that closely matches both the experimental and modelled data (single point kinetic parameter determination). The difference between experimental data and simulated results are likely a combination of the accuracy of the estimated kinetic constant, the simplify formation mechanism and the experimental error associated to particle sizing using microscopy. It is important to mention that full conversion of the silver precursor is achieved within the residence time as demonstrated experimentally [37].

To consider the effect of temperature on the apparent kinetic constant, an Arrhenius relationship was assumed. An activation energy of 120 kJ mol^{-1} for nucleation and 70 kJ mol^{-1} for growth were considered using literature data [55]. However, experimental validation of these values would be needed to enhance the accuracy of the model. The calculated values of the apparent kinetic constants at different temperatures are shown in Table 3.

3.2. Validation of the model using experimental data

In order to validate the computational model and in particular how the fluid dynamic parameters are affecting the resulting particle size distribution, different flow reactor configurations were modelled, including a straight flow reactor (SFR) and a number of helical flow reactors (HFR) with varying helix diameter (D = 14, 28 and 100 nm). As the rest of the conditions were kept constant (total flowrate: 0.7 mL min^{-1} , pitch distance: $1/\pi$, length: 0.6 m, tube inner diameter: 0.76 mm), the Reynolds number is constant across the reactors (40), with varying Dean numbers ranging from 0 in the SFR to 3.6 to 9.6 in the HFRs (see cases 1–4 in Table 1).

The dimensionless Dean number quantify the impact of the tubing curvature on flow [56], being defined as:

$$De = \sqrt{\frac{r}{R}} Re = \sqrt{\frac{r}{R}} \frac{\rho u 2r}{\mu}$$

where r is the inner radius of the tube, R is the radius of the helix, and Re is the Reynolds number. Re relates the ratio of inertial forces to viscous forces within a fluid. ρ is the fluid density, u is the average velocity at the reactor cross-section, and μ is kinematic viscosity.

In curved channels, the flow pattern is affected by centrifugal forces which promote flow towards the channel's outer wall. As Dean number increases, vortices patterns develop and increase their magnitude within the curved tubes, creating a spiral flow where elements of the fluid close to the walls of the channel move towards the centre, leading to radial

Fig. 2. Comparison of the particle size distribution of silver nanoparticles synthesised via chemical reduction in a helical flow reactor a. Experimental data and b. Simulation data. Reaction conditions: 0.05 mM silver nitrate, 0.3 mM NaBH_4 , 60C, residence time: 23 s [37]. Full experimental details are provided in the SI.

Fig. 3. A. simulated particle size distribution using coupled pbm-cfd model as a function of dean number. b. comparison of simulated and experimental mean particle size and distribution. reactor conditions: residence time: 23.3 s, T: 60 °C, total flowrate: 0.7 mL min⁻¹ (Cases 1–4 in Table 1).

mixing) that enhances mass transfer rates along with the axial primary flow [15].

Fig. 3a shows the resulting simulated silver particle size distribution at different Dean numbers, while Fig. 3b compares the simulated and the experimental average sizes where the error bars represent the standard deviation associated to the size distributions in both cases. Increasing the Dean number decreases the average particle size and reduces polydispersity with the same trends obtained in the simulated and experimental data. However, the simulated data generally presents broader size distributions, with the presence of longer size distributions tails. As previously mentioned, the difference might be associated to the experimental error in the microscopy imaging for particle sizing, the accuracy of the estimated kinetic constant or the simplify synthetic mechanism.

Particularly interesting is the size distribution of the straight flow reactor (Dean number = 0), which presents a large proportion of very small particles and a very broad size distribution. Note that this reactor configuration is experimentally unpractical as flow reactors of similar lengths (>0.5 m) must be curled to be immersed in baths for temperature control.

3.3. Importance of mixing on nucleation and growth rates

To understand the effect of the reactor geometry on the mixing of reactants, the SFR and the HFR (helix diameter: 14 mm) were considered (Cases 4 and 1, respectively in Table 1) under the same conditions, including same residence time of 23.3 s. Fig. 4a shows the concentration contours of the silver precursor due to mass transfer (diffusion and advection along the length of the reactor, without considering the synthesis of the nanoparticles). The interface between both reactants (i.e. inlet streams at time 0) is the same in both reactors (determined by the mixer). Such initial interface is not symmetrical, and it is caused by the cross-flow configuration of the mixer.

Fig. 4-b3 shows mixing index defined as $MI = 1 - \sqrt{\frac{\sigma^2}{\sigma_{max}^2}}$ with $\sigma^2 =$

$\frac{\int_A (c - \bar{c})^2 u_p dA}{\int_A u_p dA}$ along the length of the reactor (i.e. as a function of residence time). Mixing index increases sharply in the HFR, leading to complete mixing (MI = 1) after just ~ 5 s of residence time. In contrast, MI increases continuously along the length of the SFR, but MI = 1 is not achieved within the studied length. The difference is caused by the Dean vortices created by the curvature of the tube in the helical reactors, which promotes radial mixing, a phenomenon well studied in curved channels [15,37,57,58].

Mixing has profound implications for the rate at which the silver precursor is consumed during the synthesis of nanoparticles, as shown in Fig. 4-b1. The initial silver precursor consumption rate is similar in both reactors HFR and SFR during first initial ~ 4 s (Fig. 4-b3). After this time, the rate of silver precursor consumption is slower in the SFR in comparison to the HFR counterpart under the same reaction conditions. Full conversion is achieved in the HFR after ~ 13 s, while full conversion is not achieved in the SFR in the studied length (residence time of 23.3 s, Fig. 4-b3). The difference between both reactors can be explained by considering the evolution of the particle density along both reactor configurations (Fig. 4-b2). In the SFR, the low mixing index in the first seconds of the reaction leads to a small density of particles. Nucleation and growth take place along the whole reactor length, mainly at the interface between reactants [16] where particles concentrate due to the lack of radial mixing. The region where nanoparticle synthesis takes place increases along the length of the reactor, dominated by the diffusion of reactants across the initial interface. This is translated into a broad particle size distribution (continuous growth) but also the presence of very small particles (continuous nucleation), as seen in Fig. 3a. In contrast, in the HFR, the fast initial mixing is translated into nucleation taking place in the whole reaction volume with a faster overall consumption of the silver precursor. These effects could be further enhanced by breaking the stagnant regions in the centre of the Dean vortices, such as coiled flow inverter reactors [15,16,59,60].

The difference in the mixing rate in both reactor configurations leads to differences in the nucleation rate but more importantly, the extension of the volume where nucleation takes place, as defined by the following expression:

$$\bar{N}_R = \int \underbrace{k_{nuc} [BH_4^-] [Ag^+]}_{N_R} dV \Big/ \int dV \quad (16)$$

where \bar{N}_R and N_R are the overall and local nucleation rate ($\frac{\text{particles formed}}{\text{volume} \cdot \text{time}}$), respectively and V is the volume. From the expression, the localized nucleation rate (N_R) is locally higher at low levels of mixing as the local concentration of precursors ($[Ag^+]$ and $[BH_4^-]$) are higher (note that the kinetic constant is large).

Thus, N_R is relatively higher in SFR than in the HFR as the mixing is less efficient for SFR (i.e., gradients of concentration are higher at the interface) However, the extension of the active reaction volume (defined as $k_{nuc} [BH_4^-] [Ag^+] dV > 0$, where nucleation takes place) increases as the mixing rate increases. Consequently, the total rate of formation of particles \bar{N}_R , is higher in the HFR than in the SFR. Due to the higher consumption of the silver precursor in the nucleation stage in the HFR, less precursor is available for growth, resulting in a narrow size distribution.

The pronounced boundary layer in the SFR is likely to lead to fouling of the reactor as particles accumulate in the walls of the reactors, as seen in Fig. 4-b2. This is in agreement with experimental observations [61]. The Dean vortices in the HFR minimise this effect, potentially leading to lower levels of fouling. In any case, it is important to note that the model does not consider a cut-off concentration level below which nucleation does not take place. This means that nucleation will always happen when $N_R = k_{nuc} [BH_4^-] [Ag^+] > 0$. As a result, nucleation (N_R) and growth ($G_R = k_{growth} [Ag^+] [Ag]_s$) take place simultaneously along the length of the reactor. Despite this, experimental and simulation results agree well,

Fig. 4. Concentration contours of AgNO_3 along the reactor length for a straight (SFR) and a helical flow reactor (HFR). a. Considering only diffusion and advection of reactants. b1. including the consumption of reactants for the synthesis of silver nanoparticles (nucleation and growth). b2. particle density evolution for case b. and d. average AgNO_3 concentration and mixing index for case b3. Cases 1 and 4 in Table S1 (total flowrate of 0.7 mL min^{-1} , HFR has a $De = 9.6$). Time = 0 s refers to the inlet of the reactor.

which indicates that nucleation of silver takes place at almost any silver concentration in the presence of NaBH_4 .

3.4. Decoupling effects

Previous section clearly shows a direct relationship between mixing rate, nucleation and growth rates and, consequently the resulting size and distribution. The CFD with PBM model enables to decoupled parameters, understanding time-resolved effects. By varying the total flow rate, the effect of Reynolds number is studied (cases 1 + 5 to 8 on Table 1) in HFRs with the same helix diameter (14 mm). One should note that the total residence time varies, with the minimum residence time just under 8 s.

Fig. 5 a shows the concentration contours of silver precursor along

the length of the reactor considering just mixing (diffusion and advection, left) and with the addition of the synthesis of silver nanoparticles using population balance (right) for Reynolds numbers between 9 and 120. As before, the lack of symmetry on the concentration contour at time = 0 s is due to inlet effects, mostly due the introduction of the reactants using a T-mixer where the reducing agent (NaBH_4) is introduced perpendicular to the flow direction. This leads to the partial engulfment of the stream by the other stream containing the silver precursor, which increases the contact area between both streams and enhances mixing. This phenomenon is magnified as the flow rate, and thus the Reynolds number, is increased. In addition, the increase in Reynolds number increases the magnitude of the Dean vortices in the helical reactor. As the reactor has a constant geometry with a constant helical diameter of 14 mm, the shape of the Dean vortices is similar independently of the

Fig. 5. Concentration contours of AgNO₃ along the reactor length a helical flow reactor (HFR) a. Considering only diffusion and advection of reactants b. including the consumption of reactants for the synthesis of silver nanoparticles (nucleation and growth). c. mixing index, average AgNO₃ concentration and particle density evolution for case b. d. contours of particle density and e. resulting PSD for full AgNO₃ conversion. Cases 1 and 5–8 in Table 1. Time = 0 s refers to the inlet of the reactor.

flowrate. However, their magnitude increases considerably by increasing Re, resulting in a shift of the velocity profile towards the external wall of the helix due to the centrifugal flow component [37], while the stagnant zone in the centre of the vortices decreases slightly (Fig. 6). As a result of both phenomena, complete mixing of streams is very fast (within 2.5 s) for Reynolds numbers > 80, while full mixing is not achieved after 20 s when Reynolds number is 9 (Fig. 5b).

As discussed above, the differences in mixing rate have profound

effects on the synthesis of the silver nanoparticles. At high Reynolds number (>80), the fast mixing (i.e., mixing index rapid approaching 1) of the precursors results in a lower localised reaction rate but a considerably higher average reaction rate. This is translated into an initial low initial silver precursor consumption followed by a burst of nucleation with a rapid increase in the number of particles (Fig. 5c). As conclusion, fast mixing leads to a homogenous synthesis of particles resulting in small and narrow size distribution (Fig. 5e). It is interesting

Fig. 6. a. Developed velocity contour and b. Vectors of tangential velocity for the HFC as a function of Reynolds number (by varying the flowrate in a constant reactor geometry). Cases 1 and 5–8 in Table 1.

Fig. 7. Concentration contours of $AgNO_3$ along the reactor length a helical flow reactor (HFR) a. Considering only diffusion and advection of reactants b. including the consumption of reactants for the synthesis of silver nanoparticles (nucleation and growth). c. mixing index evolution. d. particle density evolution for case b. e. average $AgNO_3$ concentration and particle density evolution. (Cases 1–3 in Table 1). Time = 0 s refers to the inlet of the reactor.

to note that despite the homogeneous formation, the nanoparticles are pushed out the stagnant zone created by the Dean vortices (Fig. 5d). On the other hand, at low Reynolds number (and thus Dean number), the initial formation of the nanoparticles takes place in the interface between the two reactant streams (Fig. 5d), where the concentration is at their highest level, resulting into an initial rapid increase in silver consumption, which is slow down as the precursor is consumed (Fig. 5c). As a result of the slow mixing in this case, the synthesis of the nanoparticles is not homogeneous along the volume of the reactor, overlapping nucleation and growth of particles with the result of broad size distributions (Fig. 5e). It is worth mentioning that although full conversion is achieved at all Reynolds numbers studied at ~ 15 s (Fig. 5c), the silver precursor consumption profile depends on the Reynolds number and affects whether the precursor is primarily used for nucleation or growth.

To decouple the effect of Reynolds and Dean numbers, the Reynold

number was kept constant (41) and the Dean number varied by varying the diameter of the reactor helix (Cases 1–3, Table 1). The rest of the conditions, including the residence time are kept constant. In this case, as the total flow rate is constant, the initial silver concentration contours are the same, achieving the same level of mixing in the T-mixer. Thus, the differences in terms of particle size, distribution and density are due to the reactor configuration. The mixing index increases faster as the Dean number increases for a given Reynolds number (Fig. 7b); however, as seen before, Reynolds number also has an effect. As a result, there is a convoluted effect of both in the mixing. At the higher Dean number of 9.6, homogeneous mixing of the precursors is achieved within 5 s, while for a Dean number of 3.6, full mixing is only achieved at ~ 18 s (without considering reaction). Interestingly, a similar rate of silver consumption is achieved in all cases (Fig. 7b), including at a Dean = 0 (SFR) (note this will change at higher Reynolds numbers as discussed in previous

Fig. 8. Tangential velocity vector as a function of Dean number. Cases 1–3 in Table 1.

Fig. 9. Effect of temperature: a. concentration contour of AgNO_3 along the reactor length during the synthesis of Ag NPs b. Particle density evolution c. average AgNO_3 concentration and particle density as a function of residence time and d. particle size distribution after a residence time of 23.3 s. Cases 1, 9 and 10 in Table 1. Time = 0 s refers to the inlet of the reactor.

section). However, increasing the Dean number, in other words, increasing mixing rate, leads to an overall increase in the particle density (Fig. 7c and d), meaning that the precursor is preferentially used for nucleation rather than particle growth.

It is remarkable that at high Dean numbers (>6.5) the particles concentrate outside the stagnant volume of the Dean vortices due to the centrifugal force. However, at low Dean numbers (3.6), the opposite is observed (Fig. 7c). The reason behind this difference is that at the low end of the Dean numbers, the vortices fail to form, as shown in the tangential velocity vectors in Fig. 8, and the boundary layer around the walls under laminar flow dominates.

3.5. Effect of temperature

Temperature has a large effect on the kinetic constant for nucleation and growth but also on physical parameters such as diffusion coefficient, viscosity, and density. We have shown above that both aspects are intertwined. To decouple the effects, the effect of temperature on the resulting silver particles synthesised in a given helical reactor configuration (cases 1, 9–10 in Table 1) was studied. For this, the apparent nucleation and growth kinetic constants were assumed to follow an Arrhenius' relationship with respect to temperature with activation energies of 120 mol^{-1} and 70 kJ mol^{-1} , respectively [55]. The pre-exponential constants were estimated using the experimental data. Values for apparent kinetic constants at different temperatures given in

Table 3. The effect of temperature of physical parameters such as diffusion coefficient (Table 2) is evident in the initial concentration contours created in the T-mixer. In all cases, a clear interface between the reactant streams is observed, but a higher level of diffusion as temperature increases leads to a higher contact between streams at time = 0. Mixing rate is very fast in all cases, being dominated by the reactor configuration as shown above (e.g. Dean vortices developed very fast due to the helical configuration). As temperature increases, nucleation rate increases, leading to a burst of nuclei formation at $90 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with complete silver conversion achieved within $\sim 2\text{--}3 \text{ s}$ (Fig. 9a and d) translated into a high density of small average particle size and narrow size distribution. This is despite the increase in the simultaneous growth rate as temperature leads to a higher increase in the nucleation rate ($\sim 4\times$ nucleation kinetic constant per $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ increase in temperature) with respect to the growth rate ($\sim 2\times$ growth kinetic constant per $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ increase in temperature). This effect of temperature on the nucleation and growth kinetic constants might defer with chemical environment, reducing agent or metal considered.

As expected, the overall rate of silver consumption decreases as temperature decreases (Fig. 9d). As a result, a smaller number of particles are formed (Fig. 9d) with a higher extent of growth, which results in bigger particles and broader size distribution (Fig. 9c) in agreement with recent experimental observations [62].

4. Conclusions

This work presents an experimentally validated model to predict the average size and size distribution of silver nanoparticles synthesised in flow microreactors. Its novelty relies on the combination of population balance models using experimental kinetic data with fluid dynamic simulations. As a result, the model provides a platform for CFD-guided design of reactors by decoupling physical (e.g. temperature, concentrations), chemical (e.g. nucleation and growth rates) and reactor design (e.g. geometry, curvature) effects. The data clearly reveals that mixing has profound implications for the rate at which the silver precursor is consumed during the synthesis of nanoparticles. Evolution of the mixing index along the reactor controls the volume in which nanoparticles are formed. At low mixing rates, nanoparticle synthesis takes place in a small reaction volume at the interface between the reactant streams. Such reaction volume increases along the reactor promoted by reactants diffusion. By contrast, at high mixing rates, nucleation takes place in the whole reaction volume with a faster overall consumption of the silver precursor minimising the extension of growth, resulting in small and narrow size distribution. High mixing rates can be achieved by increasing the magnitude of Dean vortices in helical reactors, requiring a certain Reynolds number threshold. The population balance model presented here is appropriate for the silver nanoparticle case study, where silver nucleation occurs at virtually any concentration. The model provides the capability to adjust the input conditions of the reactants, analyse the impact of the mixer, modify the reactor's geometry, and investigate the operational conditions of the studied synthesis. Expansion of the model to other synthetic routes and nanomaterials will require the introduction of threshold concentrations for the nucleation and agglomeration of the particles as well as potentially more complex mechanisms. Particularly important is the need of inherent kinetic data under conditions where mixing time is considerably lower than reaction time. Overall conclusions on the effect of mixing rate will depend on the magnitude of the nucleation and growth kinetic constants as well as their ratio.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2023.147684>.

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